

Modifying $\gamma\delta$ T cells for cancer treatment: a systematic review

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Abstract

Background: $\gamma\delta$ T cells have the potential to become a competitive tool in cancer treatment, particularly through combined therapy and modifications. The objective of this review is to provide a more intuitive overview of the preclinical results of current $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modifications and to gain a general understanding of the quality of these studies.

Methods: A search of PubMed was conducted up until November, 2023 for studies applying $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modifications, including the utilization of only $\gamma\delta$ T cell membrane receptors. I designed a set of questions and adapted the SYRCLE's RoB tool to assess the integrity and risk of bias of the reviewed studies. Data on experimental methods, disease models, and cytotoxic efficacies were extracted and summarized.

Results: From the initial 4412 records, 73 studies were included, spanning a period from 2004 to 2023. The most commonly utilized strategies among the reviewed studies were chimeric antigen receptor (CAR)-T cell, T cell receptor (TCR)-T cell, and therapeutic antibodies. For cell modification, the most common method was retroviral transduction on PBMCs. The standard procedures typically involved stimulation, transduction, and expansion. The most common cell culture medium used was RPMI 1640 supplemented with fetal calf serum (FCS) and IL-2 or human AB serum and IL-2. Based on the questions I utilized for assessment, there were no significant differences in the quality of articles across these three strategies.

Conclusion: This review provided a general understanding of the methodology and

preclinical efficacy of current $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modification studies in an intuitive way. In the meantime, the questions designed to assess the integrity and risk of bias in preliminary studies can serve as a checklist for improving the overall quality of future literature phrasing. This will ultimately minimize the unnecessary time and effort waste and expedite the translation of research to clinical practice.

Keywords

$\gamma\delta$ T cell immunotherapy, cancer treatment, engineered $\gamma\delta$ T cells, $\gamma\delta$ T cell modification, bispecific antibody, CAR-T, TCR-T

Key messages

What is already known on this topic

$\gamma\delta$ T cells have been explored in various clinical trials, demonstrating approximately a 10% overall objective response rate of non-modified $\gamma\delta$ T cell expansions in the treatment of tumorous diseases. On the other hand, the modified $\gamma\delta$ T cell trial achieved a ~80% objective response, highlighting the great potential of $\gamma\delta$ T cell modification in cancer treatment. However, currently, there are insufficient clinical trials utilizing modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells to facilitate a systematic analysis of clinical treatment outcomes. Existing reviews primarily summarize strategies for the utilization of $\gamma\delta$ T cells in cancer therapy, lacking details into the preclinical effects of the designs.

What this study adds

This study is the first to undertake a systematical analysis of preclinical studies involving modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells in cancer treatment, while also evaluating the methodological integrity and risk of bias within these studies. It offers an intuitive overview of the cytotoxicity of each

design and provides a comprehensive summary of the common experimental methods employed in the included studies.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy

This systematical summary of preclinical modified $\gamma\delta$ T cell studies in treating cancerous diseases may increase the reproducibility of preclinical research outcomes. Thereby, accelerating the translation of preclinical studies into clinical applications.

Introduction

The $\gamma\delta$ T cell population, characterized by the expression of a γ chain and its pairing with a δ chain of the T cell receptor (TCR), represents approximately 4% of all T cells in human peripheral blood¹. Based on the δ chain variable gene expression, human $\gamma\delta$ T cells can be subclassified into V δ 2 T cells and non-V δ 2 T cells, with V δ 1- and V δ 3-expressing $\gamma\delta$ T cells comprising the majority of non-V δ 2 T cells². V γ 9V δ 2 T cells are the most prevalent subset in human blood. $\gamma\delta$ T cells exhibit an MHC-independent manner of antigen recognition and an inherent propensity to exhibit type one immune responses³⁻⁶, these cells have garnered significant interest in the field of adoptive cell therapy in recent years. Previously, I have reviewed the clinical outcomes of current $\gamma\delta$ T cell immunotherapy, with the majority of studies utilizing unmodified $\gamma\delta$ T cells⁷. The treatment strategies included direct stimulation, adoptive cell transfer, and the combination of cell transfer with traditional therapies. The overall objective response (OR) rate for $\gamma\delta$ T cell therapy is approximately 10%, whereas those utilizing combined therapies exhibit a pooled OR of around 35%. In addition, the trial that employed modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells in the treatment of lymphoma achieved an OR rate over 80%⁸. Combined with the tendency towards the induction of lower-grade adverse events^{7,9,10}, $\gamma\delta$ T cell immunotherapy has the potential to be a more powerful tool in cancer treatment.

However, currently there is insufficient clinical trial data on modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells, and a lack of direct summaries focused on the efficacy of preclinical results of $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modifications. Therefore, this review aims to provide a more intuitive overview of the preliminary results of $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modifications, with a focus on the cytotoxicity results of these modifications. I also reviewed the basic experimental methods and disease models. To gain a general understanding of the quality of these studies, I have designed a set of questions to assess the integrity and risk of bias based solely on the articles.

Methods

This systematic review was performed in compliance with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines.

Eligibility criteria

I aimed to encompass all publications that focused on the manipulation of $\gamma\delta$ T cells for the treatment of cancerous diseases. The inclusion criteria were as follows: (1) studies that investigated the modification of human $\gamma\delta$ T cells and its efficacy in the treatment of tumorous diseases; (2) studies that investigated the effects of therapeutic antibodies in recruiting human $\gamma\delta$ T cells for the treatment of tumorous diseases. The exclusion criteria were as follows: studies that (1) did not have *in vitro* or *in vivo* or clinical results of the modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells or antibodies in treating cancerous diseases; (2) only investigated on mice $\gamma\delta$ T cells; (3) investigated stem cells; (4) was not a research article; (5) not available in full text; (6) not in English.

Search strategy

To gain insights into the potential of engineered $\gamma\delta$ T cells in cancer treatment, I previously

identified 44 studies through literature search. These studies were either retrieved by searching the term “(engineer) AND ($\gamma\delta$ T cells)” or randomly identified during daily work. Based on these studies, I have selected several keywords for searching relevant literatures of this review. The keywords were grouped into two categories: Group A: (1) “ $\gamma\delta$ T cells”; (2) “ $\gamma\delta$ T cell”; (3) “V γ 9V δ 2 T cells”; (4) “gamma/delta”; (5) “TCR $\gamma\delta$ ”; and Group B: (1) “cancer therapy”; (2) “cancer treatment”; (3) “immunotherapy”; (4) “engineer”; (5) “modify”; (6) “modification”; (7) “gene modify”; (8) “gene modification”; (9) “gene editing”; (10) “crispr”; (11) “cas9”; (12) “chimeric antigen receptor”; (13) “CAR”; (14) “CAR-T cell”; (15) “CAR T cells”; (16) “TCR-T”; (17) “TCR transfer”; (18) “engager”; (19) “bispecific”; (20) “bispecific antibody”; (21) “ipsc”; (22) “stem cells”; (23) “stem cell”. I then conducted a search by combining “(keywords in Group A) AND (keywords in group B)” in PubMed advanced search builder on 17-20 November, 2023.

Selection process

Duplicated records were directly removed during the process of keywords searching. The collected records were initially screened based on titles and/or abstracts, and color-coded. Subsequently, highly relevant records were evaluated through full texts. The screening process was performed by one reviewer (LM).

Data collection

The following information from the included studies was collected: (1) General information (PMID, author, publication year, strategy, target, cancer type and diseases); (2) Experimental methods (transgene, transfection method, transfection protocol, effector cell type, culture method, and stimulant); (3) Outcome measures (*in vitro* model, *in vitro* cytotoxicity

assessment, *in vivo* model, and *in vivo* results). The extracted data was verified 1-3 times during the analyzing process. The data extraction process was performed by one reviewer (LM).

Study integrity and risk of bias assessment

I designed a series of questions to assess the integrity of the reviewed reports and risk of bias of the *in vitro* cytotoxic studies. In addition, based on the SYRCLE's RoB tool¹¹, I adjusted the questions for *in vivo* study assessment. Questions are provided in Supplemental Table 2. The integrity assessment included descriptions of the cell expansion method, transduction method, transgene information, and information regarding cytotoxic-related tests *in vitro* (e.g. effector-to-target ratio, therapeutic antibody concentration). Meanwhile, the assessment of risk of bias involved the designs and results of cytotoxic-related tests *in vitro* (control, error bar, and abnormal values) as well as the designs of *in vivo* experiments (randomization, baseline characteristics, and endpoint rationales). In order to make the evaluation results more intuitive, I assigned scores based on the answers. Except for the answers to "abnormal values", all other "yes" answers were scored 2, "no" scored 0, "unclear" scored 1. For the question of "abnormal values", "yes" scored 0, "no" scored 2. If a study was not relevant to a particular question, it was rated "NA" and was not counted in the number of rated items. The final score for each study was normalized as follows: totalNP = (total score) / (total number of rated items), inteNP = (total score of integrity items) / (total number of rated integrity items), biasNP = (total score of bias risk items) / (total number of rated bias risk items).

Patient and public involvement

Patients were not involved as contributors in this study.

Results

Study selection

The selection process is outlined in the flow diagram (Figure 1) and described in the Methods section. Generally, from the 44 studies that I had already identified for the study of engineered $\gamma\delta$ T cells in cancer immunotherapy, I noticed that the spelling of “ $\gamma\delta$ T cells” might influence search results. Therefore, two sets of keywords were generated from the titles or abstracts for the literature search of this review. According to the History and Search Details generated automatically from PubMed Advanced Search Builder, a total of 12273 records were retrieved. During the search process, I directly removed duplicate records, resulting in 4412 initial studies. Second, I conducted a quick color-coded screening, focusing mainly on the titles, using the keywords listed in Figure 1 to exclude 1573 unqualified records. Subsequently, another 2740 records were excluded by screening of titles and/or abstracts. The remaining 99 highly-relevant records were further examined. Of these, 27 records were excluded, and one reference study was retrieved. While 11 studies were excluded for explicit reasons such as limited accessibility, lack of relevance, non-research articles, non-English language, and not involving human $\gamma\delta$ T cells, the basic information and exclusion reasons for the other 16 studies were listed in Supplemental Table 1 (No. 1-16). Furthermore, an examination was conducted for the 21 records with lower relevance. Among these, exclusion reasons for the six most pertinent studies were included in Supplemental Table 1 (No. 17-22) as well.

Study characteristics

A total of 73 studies were included in this review, with publication dates ranging from 2004 to 2023 (Figure 2A, Supplemental Table 4). The number of published studies exhibited in increasing numbers over time. Based on the strategies employed, these 73 included studies can be classified into three main categories: (1) cell treatment (CAR-T cell and TCR-T cell); (2) antibody treatment; and (3) alternative approaches (gene modification, antibody-cell conjugation, extracellular vesicles, vaccine) (Figure 2B). I focused on both the experimental methods and the preliminary efficacies for each design (Figure 3, Figure 5, Table 1-2).

Strategies and targets

In general, over 60% of the studies explored CAR-T cell or TCR-T cell technologies on $\gamma\delta$ T cells. Additionally, 24.7% of the studies employed therapeutic antibodies, primarily in the form of bispecific antibodies (Figure 2B). Beyond traditional CAR-T cell designs, several new approaches were examined in $\gamma\delta$ T cells. These strategies included transfecting cytokine genes (IL-15 or IL-7) to enhance the persistence of modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells¹²⁻¹⁴, as well as utilizing dual targeting to improve CAR- $\gamma\delta$ T cell functions. For instance, the utilization of parallel CAR co-targeting of Mucin1 (MUC1) and epidermal growth factor receptor (ErbB) dimers¹⁵, transducing glucocorticoid-induced TNFR-related protein ligand (GIRTL) gene to trigger signals via GTR¹⁶, and combining with a secreted PD-L1/CD3 ϵ bispecific antibody to target both PD-L1-positive tumors and CAR-targeted tumors simultaneously¹⁷. Furthermore, in TCR-T cell therapy, of which utilizing the modification of TCR to endow T cell tumor-specific cytotoxicity, TCR mispairing remains a significant challenge. To overcome this, several studies have explored the domain exchange approach¹⁸ and employed the CRISPR Cas9 (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats-associated protein-9)-mediated knockout of the endogenous TCR β gene¹⁹. The domain exchange method had

also been used to enhance tumor-specific cytotoxicity in T cells²⁰. Meanwhile, TCR-T cell have been combined with antibody technology, much like the innovative efforts in CAR-T cell technology. This integration normally involves the fusion of an antibody-based binding domain, such as a single-chain variable fragment (scFV)²¹ or a Fab fragment^{8,22,23}, to the carboxy-terminal domain area of $\gamma\delta$ TCR. The antibody technologies applied in these studies can be broadly grouped into three strategies: (1) utilizing domains of $\gamma\delta$ TCR to construct antibodies^{24,25}, (2) $\gamma\delta$ T cell membrane receptors and tumor antigen-targeting bispecific antibodies²⁶⁻³¹, and (3) $\gamma\delta$ TCR and tumor antigen-targeting bispecific antibodies³²⁻⁴². The design of bispecific antibodies encompassed the utilization of a tribody format, which incorporates three binding domains^{27,29,32,33,35}, or with a nanobody (or VHH, a single-domain antibody derived from the variable domain of a heavy-chain antibody found in camelids or sharks)^{34,36,38,41}.

Beyond these, six studies explored alternative approaches for utilizing $\gamma\delta$ T cells in cancer treatment. In an effort to enhance $\gamma\delta$ T cells' resistance to chemotherapeutic agent in the treatment of glioblastoma, a resistant gene was introduced to $\gamma\delta$ T cells^{43,44}. Additionally, to overcome the inhibitory effects of the tumor microenvironment, $\gamma\delta$ T cells were genetically modified to express anti-PD-1 antibody and showed increased cytotoxicity and led to higher concentrations of PD-1 antibody within tumor conditions compared to exogenous PD-1 antibody treatment⁴⁵. Furthermore, extracellular vesicles derived from $\gamma\delta$ T cells were investigated for their potential to deliver miR-138 in the treatment of oral squamous cell carcinoma⁴⁶. $\gamma\delta$ T cell were also fused with mitomycin C-treated osteosarcoma cells to serve as vaccines that stimulate T cell immunity⁴⁷. Finally, to minimize the potential risks associated with genetic modification and enhance treatment efficiency, antibodies were chemically conjugated to $\gamma\delta$ T cells and displayed potent cytotoxicity against B cell tumors⁴⁸.

In line with the previously reviewed features regarding $\gamma\delta$ T cell-based adoptive transfer for cancer treatment⁷, the majority of studies have focused on solid tumor models. Approximately 48% of the studies have been conducted on solid cancer models, while 16% evaluated both solid and blood cancer models (Figure 2C). Among these 73 studies, a total of 112 transgene or antibody constructs were involved, including those used for controls. Notably, more than 30 tumor-specific antigens were targeted by these 112 designs (Figure 2D).

Characteristics of experimental method

To enhance the interpretation of the results, I have also collected the essential experimental-related information for each of the 112 designs (Figure 3). This information might facilitate future studies in developing novel strategies or methodologies. Within the 112 designs examined, 86 involved the utilization of CAR-T and TCR-T cell, while 20 focused on the application of therapeutic antibodies. In all 86 cell treatment designs, viral transduction (retroviral or lentiviral) and electroporation were employed, with retroviral being the most frequently used method (Figure 3A). Also, the majority of studies directly transfected PBMC instead of $\gamma\delta$ T cells (Figure 3B). Typical transduction procedure is “stimulation→transduction→expansion” for viral transduction method (Figure 3C, yellow), while for electroporation, typical procedure is “stimulation→expansion→electroporation” (Figure 3C, blue). Several studies also utilized a selection step either at the beginning or after a first expansion (Figure 3C, grey). The transduction time were slightly different between CAR-T cell method and TCR-T method (Table 1). For example, most CAR-T cell designs were transduced on day 5, while most TCR-T cell designs were transduced on day 3 or 4, however the transduction efficiency were similar (on average around 54% and 59% for

CAR-T and TCR-T) (Table 1). Furthermore, the expansion culture was examined (Table 2, Figure 3D). The most commonly used medium combinations were RPMI 1640 supplemented with FCS and IL-2 or human AB serum and IL-2. These combinations were utilized in 15 and 12 designs, respectively, and each combination was derived from 6 studies (Figure 3D). Additionally, as the majority of studies have focused on V γ 9V δ 2 T cells (Figure 3E), thus zoledronate emerged as the most frequently utilized stimulant (Table 2). Anti-CD3/CD28 beads were primarily utilized when there was a selection step involved.

Integrity and risk of bias assessment

In this systematic review, I primarily focused on investigating the *in vitro* cytotoxic capacities of $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modifications towards tumor models. Due to the lack of *in vitro* study assessment reference, and to minimizing assessment bias, I designed a set of questions which can be easily answered with 'yes' or 'no' based solely on the article itself (Supplemental Table 2). The purpose of these questions is to provide a general understanding of the integrity and risk of bias of the article. Questions for *in vivo* experiments were adjusted from SYRCLE's RoB tool¹¹. I assigned scores ranging from 0 to 2 based on the answers. Higher scores were associated with higher integrity and less risk of bias of the article. The median normalized total scores for CAR-T cell, TCR-T cell, and antibody studies were 1.8, 1.65, and 1.67, respectively, while the mean scores were 1.73, 1.62, and 1.62, respectively. There were no significant differences in normalized total scores, integrity scores and bias scores among CAR-T cell, TCR-T cell, and antibody studies (Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test and Wilcoxon rank sum test, data not shown). A summary of these assessments is provided in Figure 4, Supplemental Figure 1, and Supplemental Table 3. For studies with *in vivo* results, the majority of the descriptions were incomplete in

mentioning the three examined items regarding risk of bias. Only one or two papers mentioned blinding during experiment.

Preliminary efficacies of the reviewed designs

Due to the wide range of disease models and various experimental procedures, synthesis analyzing was not applicable. However, in order to have a clearer understanding of the preclinical effects of $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modification, I listed the range of cytotoxicity towards all tumor cell models involved in each study for each design. Most of the tumor lysis percentages were obtained from figures that did not directly indicate the corresponding numbers, necessitating a direct reading of the figures. If applicable, I selected the lysis results obtained at an effector-to-target ratio of 10:1 or similar ratios. Only tumor models positive for the target of the design were included in the results. Figure 5 provides a summary of the effects of the 112 designs from the 73 reviewed studies. In general, CAR-T cell and therapeutic antibody designs in the studies exhibited relatively improved cytotoxicity towards the tested tumor models both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. It should be noted that in this study, I grouped the TEG (T cells engineered to express a defined $\gamma\delta$ T cell receptor) studies⁴⁹⁻⁵³ into the TCR-T category, despite researchers defined them as the next generation of CAR-T cell technology. Despite this, overall, the TCR-T cell studies were more exploratory, such as focusing on reducing the mispairing of endogenous and introduced TCRs. In addition, several designs have already proceeded to clinical trials^{8,48,50,52-54}.

Discussion

$\gamma\delta$ T cells are the immune cell type most strongly associated with favorable prognosis in cancers⁵⁵. Compared with $\alpha\beta$ T cells, the immune response elicited by $\gamma\delta$ T cells is generally

more rapid and tends towards a type I immune response^{56,57}. Their MHC-independent characteristics make it easier and safer to achieve allogeneic transplantation, increasing the possibility of 'off-the-shelf' supply of therapeutic cells.

In this systematic review, I have attempted to provide a more intuitive summary of the preclinical research progress involving $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modifications. Currently, there is a lack of similar reviews that focus on the preliminary outcomes of $\gamma\delta$ T cell therapy, despite the fact that such results might be less important in guiding clinical practice. However, several reviews have well summarized the strategies for developing $\gamma\delta$ T cell-based immunotherapies⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹. These reviews were in line with our findings regarding the strategies for modifying $\gamma\delta$ T cells. In addition, the reviewed studies covered the treatment of both hematological and solid cancers, and the studied targets were representative of those commonly targeted in current cell therapies. Regarding the research method, despite the examination of cytotoxic effects towards tumor models, most studies also investigated the phenotypes of modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells, such as the activation and exhaustion levels. This information is useful for developing new strategies to enhance the efficacy within tumor microenvironment (TME). Also, studies have focused on cytokine productions, particularly IFN γ . This result is not only relevant to the cytotoxic potential against tumor cells but it can also serve as an indicator for the safety of the application of modified $\gamma\delta$ T cell. For example, the innovative antibody-conjugated $\gamma\delta$ T cells showed excellent cytotoxicity towards tumor models; but they also exhibited concerning levels of IFN γ induction following tumor cell activation and cytotoxicity towards normal cells⁴⁸. Moreover, given the significant variations across studies, it is challenging to draw definitive conclusions for the effectiveness of the designs. According to the results I collected, therapeutic antibodies and CAR-T cell modifications have shown promising potential in enhancing the efficacy of $\gamma\delta$ T cell

immunotherapy. Furthermore, the $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related TCR modification offers a promising solution to address the current disadvantages associated with $\alpha\beta$ TCR-T cell therapies, as well as providing a potential method to overcome the limitations in $\gamma\delta$ T cell expansion.

As preliminary studies were or should be of various approaches, the purpose of this systematic review is solely to provide a summary or index of the preliminary results of $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modifications. Given the enhanced readability of graphical representations, I have managed to present the range of tumor lysis percentages in Figure 5. It should be noted, however, that the numbers extracted from the reviewed studies were obtained through direct interpretation of figures and may not reflect precise numbers. Also, the range covered the lysis percentages to multiple tumor cell lines, with the intention of providing a comprehensive overview rather than making direct comparisons. I did not distinguish the lysis results of studies that also utilized $\gamma\delta$ T cell stimulants (e.g. zoledronate) during coculture with tumor cells. In terms of the summary of experimental method, it is important to note that the cell culture during transduction may differ from the expansion culture. Also, as many studies used “after x days” rather than “on day x” to indicate the transduction time point, there may be a one-day discrepancy in the timepoint listed in Table 1.

During the review process, I only searched using PubMed and limited to English-language articles. I observed that different terminologies for “ $\gamma\delta$ T cells” could influence search results, and I utilized various combinations of keywords to ensure the coverage of relevant reports (see Methods). Nevertheless, there remains a possibility that some relevant studies may have been overlooked. Moreover, the screening and data collection processes were conducted by a single reviewer, which might involve higher risk of missing relevant studies⁶⁰. In addition, I designed the assessment questions based solely on the article, and did not contact study authors to clarify unclear information. Lastly, the current review excluded

studies on induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) (Supplemental Table 1), due to the fact that iPSC-based approaches mainly involve manipulating culture techniques without direct gene modification. Also, there is controversy with the authenticity of iPSC-derived $\gamma\delta$ T cells, with debate over the safety of “mimetic” ones for clinical applications^{61,62}.

Given the diverse nature of preliminary studies, a systematic review of these investigations should not impose any constraints on future explorations, as it is intended to provide a comprehensive overview rather than dictate specific directions or boundaries. Nevertheless, a retrospective analysis of preliminary studies can help to reduce unnecessary waste of time and effort and to improve the reproducibility among research groups. Based on the findings of this review, several implications are worth considering for future studies. Firstly, to make $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related articles be more discoverable, it is recommended to utilize more widely recognized terminology to describe $\gamma\delta$ T cells. Also, to facilitate the distinction between $\gamma\delta$ T cell cancers (e.g., $\gamma\delta$ T cell lymphoma) and the application of $\gamma\delta$ T cells in the treatment of cancerous diseases, it may be beneficial to use alternative phrasing. For example, using “gammadelta” instead of “ $\gamma\delta$ ” to indicate $\gamma\delta$ T cell cancers can simplify the screening process, even though it does not affect the search results. Secondly, with regards to the description of experimental methods in related studies, it is recommended to indicate the cell culture duration and timepoint of transduction precisely. For *in vivo* experiments, it is advisable to specify the baseline information of model animals and rationale for endpoint selection. If feasible, it would be beneficial to provide schematic diagrams or sequence information of the transgene. This information is crucial for ensuring reproducibility and may even enabling analytical comparisons across different laboratories for certain studies. These kinds of analyses can enhance the reliability of preclinical research results and expedite the transition from research to clinical application. Thirdly, as typical $\gamma\delta$ T cells have

the inherent ability to exert cytotoxic effects towards tumor cells¹, enhancing their tumor specificity represents the most straightforward strategy. However, it is essential to keep in mind that these cells are natural infiltrators with positive attributes in defeating tumors⁵⁵, which raises the significance of the long-term tumor environment as a factor that impedes their cytotoxic effects. Therefore, it is worthwhile to explore strategies aimed at enhancing the infiltrating capacity, persistence, and abundance of effector $\gamma\delta$ T cells within different tumor environments. In addition, in my previous review on $\gamma\delta$ T cell immunotherapy⁷, I noticed that combinational treatment generally exhibited improved efficacy in tumor treatments. Therefore, it is of significant value to investigate the mechanisms of traditional cancer treatments in influencing the tumor environment and assessing whether these are associated with enhancing the infiltrating capacity and persistence of $\gamma\delta$ T cells.

Abbreviations

CAR	chimeric antigen receptor
CRISPR Cas9	clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats-associated protein-9
ErbB	epidermal growth factor receptor
FCS	fetal calf serum
GITR	glucocorticoid-induced TNFR-related protein ligand
iPSC	induced pluripotent stem cell
MUC1	Mucin1
OR	objective response
scFV	single-chain variable fragment
TCR	T cell receptor
TEG	T cells engineered to express a defined $\gamma\delta$ T cell receptor
TME	tumor microenvironment

Table 1 Efficiency of viral transduction and electroporation

Strategy	Method	Viral transduction/electroporation time	Efficiency (%+)
CAR-T	retroviral	d3(n=3), d4-5(n=4), d5(n=15), d8(n=1)	25%~>95%(n=17/27)
	lentiviral	d2(n=2), d3(n=3), d7-9(n=2), d10(n=1)	40%~69.5%(n=6/8)
	electroporation	d0(n=1), d10-11(n=2), d12(n=2), d14(n=2), d17(n=5), d21(n=1)	30.7%~89.19%(n=8/15)
TCR-T	retroviral	d2-3(n=1), d3(n=6), d3or5(n=1), d4(n=6)	25%~90%(n=8/25)
	lentiviral	d1(n=1), d2(n=2), d3(n=1)	36%~90%(n=3/5)
	electroporation	d7(n=1), d10-11(n=2)	10.06%~70%(n=3/3)

Table 2 Summary of the most frequently used materials for expansion

		Number of studies	Number of designs
Culture medium	RPMI 1640	23	47
	X-VIVO 15	6	8
	OpTmizer (or CTS OpTmizer)	5	8
	AIM-V	4	8
Serum	human AB serum	12	25
	FBS	12	19
	FCS	7	17
	human serum	7	12
	serum-free	4	6
Cytokine	IL-2	39	74
	IL-15	14	22
	IL-7	8	10
	IL-21	3	3
	IL-4	2	2
Stimulant	zoledronate	21	38
	anti-CD3/CD28	15	15
	anti-CD3	13	14
	with feeder cells (including K562a)	10	14

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Supplemental Table 1 Characteristics of excluded studies

PMID	Author	Year	Strategy	Target	Transgene	Exclusion reason	No
35879361	Dekkers JF	2023	BEHAV3D	-	-	mechanism study	1
29769244	Chan WK	2018	bi	CS1-NKG2D	CS1 scFV-NKG2D scFV	not indicating $\gamma\delta$ T cells effects	2
30699986	Li Z	2019	bi/DNA	MUC1-CD16	MUC1 aptamer-60nt DNA spacers-CD16 aptamer	not indicating $\gamma\delta$ T cells effects	3
28450393	Skegrod D	2017	bi, domain exchange	-	-	structure study	4
27373969	de Bruin RCG	2016	VHH(nanobody)	V γ 9V δ 2 TCR VHH	-	generation of V γ 9V δ 2 T cell-specific nanobody	5
27823582	Bethune MT	2016	domain exchange	MART1	F5 $\alpha\beta$ TCR ectodomain+ $\gamma\delta$ TCR endodomain	mispairing/safety study	6
34172580	Mallis RJ	2021	TCR-T, domain exchange	not applicable	DP10.7 $\gamma\delta$ TCR constant domain replaced by $\alpha\beta$ TCR	structure study	7
37720098	Ishihara M	2023	TCR-T	NY-ESO-1	G50A + A51E $\alpha\beta$ TCR and CD8 $\alpha\beta$	mechanism study focused on mitochondria	8
23934177	Themeli M	2013	CAR, iPSC	CD19	CD19-CD28 CAR	CAR-transduced T cell clone-derived iPSC to generate innate $\gamma\delta$	9
29164800	Watanabe D	2018	iPSC	-	-	$\gamma\delta$ T cell-derived iPSC generation	10
31071196	Zeng J	2019	iPSC	-	-	$\gamma\delta$ T cell-derived iPSC to generate NKRs-expressing mimetic V γ	11
34685611	Boyd N	2021	iPSC	-	-	cord blood hematopoietic stem cell (HSC)-derived iPSC to	12
34687276	Hosaka N	2021	iPSC	-	-	HSC-enriched bone marrow cell-derived mouse $\gamma\delta$ T cell to	13
36963392	Murai N	2023	iPSC	-	-	$\gamma\delta$ T cell-derived iPSC to generate naturally existing cytotoxic $\gamma\delta$	14
27260209	Sutton KS	2016	serum-free expansion and	none	EGFP	serum-free expansion method, modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells did not tested	15
30628681	Wang RN	2019	expansion/transduction	none	EGFP	expansion and transduction method optimizing, no cytotoxicity	16
21282338	Zhang T	2011	bi	NKG2D-CD3	CD3 scFv-NKG2D	mice	17
31318724	Hoeres T	2019	antibody	CD20	-	no $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modification	18
37654012	Wang X	2023	$\gamma\delta$ T cell extracellular	Tumor-associated	-	no modification	19
36310028	Jeon SB	2023	iPSC	-	-	pluripotent stem cell via hemogenic endothelium to generate	20
30038626	Juraske C	2018	antibody	CD3	-	no $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modification	21
21109686	Braza MS	2011	antibody	CD20	-	no $\gamma\delta$ T cell-related modification	22

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Supplemental Table 2 Questions for evaluating the reviewed papers

Category	Component	No.	Questions	Name in Sup. Table 3	Rate			
Integrity Assessment	Cell culture and stimulation	1	Is it clear which kind of culture medium was/were used?	Medium	yes	no	unclear	NA
		2	Is it clear which kind of serum was/were used? (including serum-free condition)	Serum	yes	no	unclear	NA
		3	Is it clear which kind of cytokine was/were used during cell culture?	Cytokine	yes	no	unclear	NA
		4	Is it clear which kind of stimulant was/were used to active cells?	Stimulant	yes	no	unclear	NA
		5	Is it clear how long the cells were cultured?	Culture.time	yes	no	unclear	NA
	Transduction method	6	Is the transduction time clear?	Transduction.time	yes	no	unclear	NA
		7	Is the transduction efficiency clearly mentioned?	Transduction.efficiency	yes	no	unclear	NA
	Transgene information	8	If involved, is the transgene sequence available? or is the structure illustrated in schematic diagrams?	Gene.structure.or.sequence	yes	no	unclear	NA
	Experimental illustration	9	Is the Effector : Target ratio clearly indicated in in vitro cytotoxicity test?	ET	yes	no	unclear	NA
		10	If involved, is the concentration of antibody used in the in vitro cytotoxicity test clearly mentioned?	Antibody.concentration	yes	no	unclear	NA
Risk of bias assessment	In vitro cytotoxicity	11	Is there a control group? (either for effector cells or for target cells)	Control	yes	no	unclear	NA
		12	Is there an error bar or a range of the results in the cytotoxicity figure?	Error.bar	yes	no	unclear	NA
		13	Are there abnormal values? (e.g. >100% or <0%)	Abnormal.value	yes	no	unclear	NA
	In vivo	14	Does it mention random grouping?	Random	yes	no	unclear	NA
		15	Is the age, sex, and weight of the model animal clear? (by sentence or figure)	Mice.age.sex.weight	yes	no	unclear	NA
		16	Is the reason/standard for choosing the endpoint of in vivo test clearly mentioned?	Endpoint	yes	no	unclear	NA

5 **Supplemental Table 4 List of included studies**

No	PMID	Author	Year	Strategy	ref	No	PMID	Author	Year	Strategy	ref
1	18782650	Wang Z	2008	antibody	²⁴	38	35709135	Zhang X	2022	CAR	⁶³
2	23920126	Zheng J	2013	antibody	²⁵	39	37078788	Huang SW	2023	CAR	¹⁷
3	24448235	Oberg HH	2014	antibody	³²	40	37387794	Becker SA	2023	CAR	²⁶
4	25979810	Oberg HH	2015	antibody	³³	41	37446055	Wang Y	2023	CAR	¹⁶
5	27825135	Schiller CB	2016	antibody	²⁷	42	37134157	Frieling JS	2023	CAR	⁶⁴
6	28708284	Peipp M	2017	antibody	²⁸	43	37938576	Lee D	2023	CAR	¹⁴
7	29296532	de Bruin RCG	2017	antibody	³⁴	44	37770968	Wang Y	2023	CAR	⁶⁵
8	29725336	Oberg HH	2018	antibody	²⁹	45	28818060	Harrer DC	2017	CAR, TCR-T	⁶⁶
9	32588076	Guo Q	2020	antibody	³⁰	46	30594069	Li L	2019	extracellular vesicles (gdTDEs)	⁴⁶
10	31833593	Oberg HH	2020	antibody	³⁵	47	23326319	Lamb LS Jr	2013	gene modification	⁴³
11	33177109	de Weerd I	2021	antibody	³⁶	48	34702850	Lamb LS	2021	gene modification	⁴⁴
12	33526858	Ganesan R	2021	antibody	³⁷	49	37857598	Wang Y	2023	gene modification	⁴⁵
13	33451981	de Weerd I	2021	antibody	³⁸	50	16540688	van der Veken LT	2006	TCR-T	⁶⁷
14	34815357	van Diest E	2021	antibody	³⁹	51	19242528	Hiasa A	2009	TCR-T	⁶⁸
15	34040604	Yang R	2021	antibody	³¹	52	21566093	Marcu-Malina V	2011	TCR-T	⁶⁹
16	36096643	Lai AY	2022	antibody	⁴⁰	53	21909128	Zhao H	2012	TCR-T	²⁰
17	36868236	Lameris R	2023	antibody	⁴¹	54	23018643	Gründer C	2012	TCR-T	⁷⁰
18	36685546	van Diest E	2023	antibody	⁴²	55	26121617	Shimizu K	2015	TCR-T	⁷¹
19	37835538	Li HK	2023	antibody-cell conjugation	⁴⁸	56	25991821	Straetemans T	2015	TCR-T	⁷²
20	15287953	Rischer M	2004	CAR	⁷³	57	27463149	He K	2016	TCR-T	⁷⁴
21	23295945	Deniger DC	2013	CAR	⁷⁵	58	28259946	Tao C	2017	TCR-T	¹⁸
22	27598655	Du SH	2016	CAR	⁷⁶	59	29122757	Legut M	2018	TCR-T	¹⁹
23	28341563	Fisher J	2017	CAR	⁷⁷	60	30552102	Benveniste PM	2018	TCR-T	⁷⁸
24	29310916	Capsomidis A	2018	CAR	⁷⁹	61	29899740	Straetemans T	2018	TCR-T	⁴⁹
25	29402645	Xiao L	2018	CAR	⁸⁰	62	30479831	Xu Y	2018	TCR-T	²²
26	31824502	Polito VA	2019	CAR	⁸¹	63	30871629	Johanna I	2019	TCR-T	⁵⁰
27	31506382	Fisher J	2019	CAR	⁸²	64	32019779	Janssen A	2020	TCR-T	⁸³
28	32714329	Rozenbaum M	2020	CAR	⁸⁴	65	31585951	Kierkels	2019	TCR-T	⁵¹
29	32671190	Fleischer LC	2020	CAR	⁸⁵	66	32022317	Johanna I	2020	TCR-T	⁵²
30	32462079	Ang WX	2020	CAR	⁸⁶	67	32780528	Ichiki Y	2020	TCR-T	⁸⁷
31	33520361	Zhai X	2021	CAR	⁸⁸	68	34575700	Strijker JGM	2021	TCR-T	⁵³
32	34916256	Makkouk A	2021	CAR	¹²	69	34759930	Johanna I	2021	TCR-T	⁸⁹
33	35136603	Nishimoto KP	2022	CAR	⁵⁴	70	35776199	He P	2023	TCR-T	⁸
34	35711450	Ferry GM	2022	CAR	⁹⁰	71	37349298	Chen Z	2023	TCR-T	²¹
35	35295709	Ye X	2022	CAR	¹³	72	36681817	Li C	2023	TCR-T	²³
36	36162920	Sánchez Martínez D	2022	CAR	⁹¹	73	32368439	Wang Y	2018	vaccine	⁴⁷
37	35496793	Parente-Pereira AC	2022	CAR	¹⁵						

6

7 **Legend**

8

9 **Figure 1 Flow diagram of study selection and inclusion criteria**

10

11 **Figure 2 Overview of the characteristics of the included studies**

12 **A.** Publication year and strategies of the included studies (n=73). Each color represents one
13 strategy, while each block corresponds to an individual study. **B.** Breakdown of the
14 strategies utilized in the included studies. Top, the percentage of each strategy applied
15 across the 73 studies; bottom, detailed breakdown of the three main strategies (CAR-T in
16 yellow, TCR-T in beige, therapeutic antibody in blue) utilized in each design (n=106). CAR-
17 T+ comprises 6 studies investigated new approaches (PMID: 34916256, 35295709,
18 35496793, 37078788, 37446055, 37938576); TCR-T+ comprises 8 studies utilized partial TCR
19 or combined with other stimulated molecule or modifications (PMID: 36681817, 21909128,
20 28259946, 29122757, 35776199, 37349298, 37349298, 30479831); bi: bispecific; tri:
21 triplebody; bi/tri: duel-targeting triplebody; ns: not $\gamma\delta$ TCR specific. **C.** Distribution of
22 targeted disease types (n=73). **D.** Molecular target of the designs from the included studies
23 (n=112). The number indicated in each column (**B, D**) represents the count of the designs
24 that target the corresponding molecule.

25

26 **Figure 3 Characteristics of the methodologies of the included studies**

27 **A.** Distribution of transduction methods utilized in cell treatment designs (n=86). The
28 numbers on the columns represent the count of the designs that utilized the indicated
29 transduction method. **B.** Distribution of transduced cell types in cell treatment designs
30 (n=86). The numbers represent the count of designs utilizing the indicated transduced cells.

31 The color of the number indicates the strategy of the design, with TCR-T cell designs in red
32 and CAR-T cell designs in black. **C.** Schematic representation of the typical steps in the
33 transduction procedures. The color of the lines represents the transduction type, with yellow
34 indicating viral transduction (including retroviral and lentiviral) and blue indicating
35 electroporation. Green represents the steps common to both transduction types, while grey
36 represents steps utilized in some of the studies. Solid lines connect steps utilized across all
37 studies, whereas dashed lines connect steps applied in part of the studies. The linewidth
38 positively correlates with the number of studies utilizing the corresponding transduction
39 method. The numbers indicate the count of studies encompassing the two connected steps.
40 **D.** Combinations of cell culture media and supplements in cell treatment designs (n=86).
41 Color indicates serum usage, and the size of the bubble indicates the number of designs
42 utilizing the specified combination. **E.** Effector cells utilized in cell treatment designs (n=112).
43 The colors represent the strategy type, and the numbers indicate the total count of designs
44 utilizing the corresponding effector cell.

45

46 **Figure 4 Integrity and bias assessment**

47 Based on the questions listed in supplemental table 2, normalized scores for each included
48 study were calculated using the mean value (see methods), where normalized score = sum
49 of the scores / sum of the rated item count. intelNP represents the normalized score of
50 integrity items; biasNP represents the normalized score of bias items; and totalNP
51 represents the normalized score of total rated items. The score distribution of each strategy
52 group is presented for each assessment. The red line indicates the median score, while the
53 black line indicates the 25-75% range of each strategy group. Notably, there are four groups
54 consist of only one study each. n=73.

55

56 **Figure 5 Overview of each design**

57 For cell treatment designs, the transgene is listed. For therapeutic antibody designs, the
58 target molecule is listed. In the cytotoxicity column, the dashed line in the middle indicates
59 50% cytotoxicity, the blue block indicates the mean value, and the range indicates the
60 minimum and maximum values. n=112.

61

62 **Table 1 Efficiency of viral transduction and electroporation**

63 n=83 (designs). In the efficiency column, the numbers in bracket represent the number of
64 designs with transduction efficiency and the total number of designs, respectively. Efficiency
65 results obtained from mGFP control, Jurkat cells or by MFI were not included. d: day.

66

67 **Table 2 Summary of the most frequently used materials for expansion**

68 A total of 86 CAR-T cell or TCR-T cell designs within 49 studies were examined. The number
69 was counted based on the presence of the mentioned variable in each study or design. For
70 cytokines and stimulant, they can be presented in various combinations.

71

72 **Supplemental Figure 1 Integrity and bias assessment of each study**

73 The normalized score for each included study was calculated based on the questions listed
74 in supplemental table 2. The PMID of each study was shown on the Y-axis. intelNP
75 represents the normalized score of integrity items; biasNP represents the normalized score
76 of bias items; and totalNP represents the normalized score of total rated items. The color
77 used in the figure indicates the specific strategy employed.

78

79 **Supplemental Table 1 Characteristics of excluded studies**

80 **BEHAV3D**: a multispectral, 3D image-based platform, to study the dynamic interactions of
81 immune cells and patient cancer organoids by means of imaging and transcriptomics; **bi**:
82 bispecific; **CS1**: CD319 or SLAMF7; **MUC1**: Mucin1; **VHH**: nanobody, the variable antigen
83 binding region of heavy chain only antibodies; **MART1**: melanoma-associated antigen
84 recognized by T cells; **NY-ESO-1**: New York esophageal squamous cell carcinoma 1; **iPSC**:
85 induced pluripotent stem cell; **NKR**: natural killer cell receptors.

86

87 **Supplemental Table 2 Questions for evaluating the reviewed papers**

88 For question 1-12 and 14-16: 'Yes': 2 points, can be clearly find; 'No': 0 point, cannot find;
89 'unclear': 1 point, can be vaguely distinguished; 'NA': no point, not applicable.

90 For question 13: 'Yes': 0 point, have abnormal values; 'No': 2 points, no abnormal values;
91 'unclear': 1 point, cannot be sure; 'NA': no point, not applicable.

92

93 **Supplemental Table 3 Rate of integrity and risk of bias**

94

95 **Supplemental Table 4 List of included studies**

96

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References

- 104 1. Silva-Santos B, Serre K, Norell H. $\gamma\delta$ T cells in cancer. *Nat Rev Immunol*.
105 2015;15(11):683-691. doi:10.1038/nri3904
- 106 2. Papadopoulou M, Sanchez Sanchez G, Vermijlen D. Innate and adaptive $\gamma\delta$ T cells: How,
107 when, and why. *Immunol Rev*. 2020;298(1):99-116. doi:10.1111/imr.12926
- 108 3. Silva-Santos B, Mensurado S, Coffelt SB. $\gamma\delta$ T cells: pleiotropic immune effectors with
109 therapeutic potential in cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer*. 2019;19(7):392-404.
110 doi:10.1038/s41568-019-0153-5
- 111 4. Adams EJ, Gu S, Luoma AM. Human gamma delta T cells: Evolution and ligand
112 recognition. *Cell Immunol*. 2015;296(1):31-40. doi:10.1016/j.cellimm.2015.04.008
- 113 5. Rigau M, Ostrouska S, Fulford TS, et al. Butyrophilin 2A1 is essential for phosphoantigen
114 reactivity by $\gamma\delta$ T cells. *Science*. 2020;367(6478). doi:10.1126/science.aay5516
- 115 6. Karunakaran MM, Willcox CR, Salim M, et al. Butyrophilin-2A1 Directly Binds Germline-
116 Encoded Regions of the V γ 9V δ 2 TCR and Is Essential for Phosphoantigen Sensing.
117 *Immunity*. 2020;52(3):487-498.e6. doi:10.1016/j.immuni.2020.02.014
- 118 7. Ma L, Feng Y, Zhou Z. A close look at current $\gamma\delta$ T-cell immunotherapy. *Front Immunol*.
119 2023;14:1140623. doi:10.3389/fimmu.2023.1140623
- 120 8. He P, Liu H, Zimdahl B, et al. A novel antibody-TCR (AbTCR) T-cell therapy is safe and
121 effective against CD19-positive relapsed/refractory B-cell lymphoma. *J Cancer Res Clin*
122 *Oncol*. 2023;149(7):2757-2769. doi:10.1007/s00432-022-04132-9
- 123 9. Zhang T, Chen J, Niu L, et al. Clinical Safety and Efficacy of Locoregional Therapy
124 Combined with Adoptive Transfer of Allogeneic $\gamma\delta$ T Cells for Advanced Hepatocellular
125 Carcinoma and Intrahepatic Cholangiocarcinoma. *J Vasc Interv Radiol*. 2022;33(1):19-
126 27.e3. doi:10.1016/j.jvir.2021.09.012
- 127 10. Xu Y, Xiang Z, Alnaggar M, et al. Allogeneic V γ 9V δ 2 T-cell immunotherapy exhibits
128 promising clinical safety and prolongs the survival of patients with late-stage lung or
129 liver cancer. *Cell Mol Immunol*. 2021;18(2):427-439. doi:10.1038/s41423-020-0515-7
- 130 11. Hooijmans CR, Rovers MM, Vries RBM de, Leenaars M, Ritskes-Hoitinga M, Langendam
131 MW. SYRCLE's risk of bias tool for animal studies. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2014;14:43.
132 doi:10.1186/1471-2288-14-43
- 133 12. Makkouk A, Yang XC, Barca T, et al. Off-the-shelf V δ 1 gamma delta T cells engineered
134 with glypican-3 (GPC-3)-specific chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) and soluble IL-15
135 display robust antitumor efficacy against hepatocellular carcinoma. *J Immunother*
136 *Cancer*. 2021;9(12). doi:10.1136/jitc-2021-003441
- 137 13. Ye X, Deng X, Wen J, et al. Folate Receptor-Alpha Targeted 7x19 CAR- $\gamma\delta$ T Suppressed
138 Triple-Negative Breast Cancer Xenograft Model in Mice. *J Oncol*. 2022;2022:2112898.
139 doi:10.1155/2022/2112898
- 140 14. Lee D, Dunn ZS, Guo W, et al. Unlocking the potential of allogeneic V δ 2 T cells for
141 ovarian cancer therapy through CD16 biomarker selection and CAR/IL-15 engineering.
142 *Nat Commun*. 2023;14(1):6942. doi:10.1038/s41467-023-42619-2
- 143 15. Parente-Pereira AC, Beatson RE, Davies DM, et al. Generation and application of TGF β -
144 educated human V γ 9V δ 2 T cells. *STAR Protoc*. 2022;3(2):101319.
145 doi:10.1016/j.xpro.2022.101319

- 146 16. Wang Y, Wang L, Seo N, et al. CAR-Modified V γ 9V δ 2 T Cells Propagated Using a Novel
147 Bisphosphonate Prodrug for Allogeneic Adoptive Immunotherapy. *Int J Mol Sci*.
148 2023;24(13). doi:10.3390/ijms241310873
- 149 17. Huang S-W, Pan C-M, Lin Y-C, et al. BiTE-Secreting CAR- $\gamma\delta$ T as a Dual Targeting
150 Strategy for the Treatment of Solid Tumors. *Adv Sci (Weinh)*. 2023;10(17):e2206856.
151 doi:10.1002/advs.202206856
- 152 18. Tao C, Shao H, Zhang W, et al. $\gamma\delta$ TCR immunoglobulin constant region domain
153 exchange in human $\alpha\beta$ TCRs improves TCR pairing without altering TCR gene-modified
154 T cell function. *Mol Med Rep*. 2017;15(4):1555-1564. doi:10.3892/mmr.2017.6206
- 155 19. Legut M, Dolton G, Mian AA, Ottmann OG, Sewell AK. CRISPR-mediated TCR
156 replacement generates superior anticancer transgenic T cells. *Blood*. 2018;131(3):311-
157 322. doi:10.1182/blood-2017-05-787598
- 158 20. Zhao H, Xi X, Cui L, He W. CDR3 δ -grafted $\gamma\delta$ 2T cells mediate effective antitumor
159 reactivity. *Cell Mol Immunol*. 2012;9(2):147-154. doi:10.1038/cmi.2011.28
- 160 21. Chen Z, Lin C, Pei H, et al. Antibody-based binding domain fused to TCR γ chain
161 facilitates T cell cytotoxicity for potent anti-tumor response. *Oncogenesis*. 2023;12(1):33.
162 doi:10.1038/s41389-023-00480-4
- 163 22. Xu Y, Yang Z, Horan LH, et al. A novel antibody-TCR (AbTCR) platform combines Fab-
164 based antigen recognition with gamma/delta-TCR signaling to facilitate T-cell
165 cytotoxicity with low cytokine release. *Cell Discov*. 2018;4:62. doi:10.1038/s41421-018-
166 0066-6
- 167 23. Li C, Zhou F, Wang J, et al. Novel CD19-specific $\gamma\delta$ TCR-T cells in relapsed or refractory
168 diffuse large B-cell lymphoma. *J Hematol Oncol*. 2023;16(1):5. doi:10.1186/s13045-023-
169 01402-y
- 170 24. Wang Z, Zhang T, Hu H, et al. Targeting solid tumors via T cell receptor
171 complementarity-determining region 3delta in an engineered antibody. *Cancer Lett*.
172 2008;272(2):242-252. doi:10.1016/j.canlet.2008.07.015
- 173 25. Zheng J, Guo Y, Ji X, Cui L, He W. A novel antibody-like TCR $\gamma\delta$ -Ig fusion protein exhibits
174 antitumor activity against human ovarian carcinoma. *Cancer Lett*. 2013;341(2):150-158.
175 doi:10.1016/j.canlet.2013.07.036
- 176 26. Becker SA, Petrich BG, Yu B, et al. Enhancing the effectiveness of $\gamma\delta$ T cells by mRNA
177 transfection of chimeric antigen receptors or bispecific T cell engagers. *Mol Ther*
178 *Oncolytics*. 2023;29:145-157. doi:10.1016/j.omto.2023.05.007
- 179 27. Schiller CB, Braciak TA, Fenn NC, et al. CD19-specific triplebody SPM-1 engages NK and
180 $\gamma\delta$ T cells for rapid and efficient lysis of malignant B-lymphoid cells. *Oncotarget*.
181 2016;7(50):83392-83408. doi:10.18632/oncotarget.13110
- 182 28. Peipp M, Wesch D, Oberg H-H, et al. CD20-Specific Immunoligands Engaging NKG2D
183 Enhance $\gamma\delta$ T Cell-Mediated Lysis of Lymphoma Cells. *Scand J Immunol*.
184 2017;86(4):196-206. doi:10.1111/sji.12581
- 185 29. Oberg HH, Kellner C, Gonnermann D, et al. Tribody (HER2) \times CD16 Is More Effective
186 Than Trastuzumab in Enhancing $\gamma\delta$ T Cell and Natural Killer Cell Cytotoxicity Against
187 HER2-Expressing Cancer Cells. *Front Immunol*. 2018;9:814.
188 doi:10.3389/fimmu.2018.00814
- 189 30. Guo Q, Zhao P, Zhang Z, et al. TIM-3 blockade combined with bispecific antibody
190 MT110 enhances the anti-tumor effect of $\gamma\delta$ T cells. *Cancer Immunol Immunother*.
191 2020;69(12):2571-2587. doi:10.1007/s00262-020-02638-0
- 192 31. Yang R, Shen S, Gong C, et al. Bispecific Antibody PD-L1 \times CD3 Boosts the Anti-Tumor
193 Potency of the Expanded V γ 2V δ 2 T Cells. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12:654080.

- 194 doi:10.3389/fimmu.2021.654080
- 195 32. Oberg H-H, Peipp M, Kellner C, et al. Novel bispecific antibodies increase $\gamma\delta$ T-cell
196 cytotoxicity against pancreatic cancer cells. *Cancer Res.* 2014;74(5):1349-1360.
197 doi:10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-13-0675
- 198 33. Oberg H-H, Kellner C, Gonnermann D, et al. $\gamma\delta$ T cell activation by bispecific antibodies.
199 *Cell Immunol.* 2015;296(1):41-49. doi:10.1016/j.cellimm.2015.04.009
- 200 34. Bruin RCG de, Veluchamy JP, Loughheed SM, et al. A bispecific nanobody approach to
201 leverage the potent and widely applicable tumor cytolytic capacity of V γ 9V δ 2-T cells.
202 *Oncoimmunology.* 2017;7(1):e1375641. doi:10.1080/2162402X.2017.1375641
- 203 35. Oberg H-H, Janitschke L, Sulaj V, et al. Bispecific antibodies enhance tumor-infiltrating T
204 cell cytotoxicity against autologous HER-2-expressing high-grade ovarian tumors. *J*
205 *Leukoc Biol.* 2020;107(6):1081-1095. doi:10.1002/JLB.5MA1119-265R
- 206 36. Weerdt I de, Lameris R, Scheffer GL, et al. A Bispecific Antibody Antagonizes Prosurvival
207 CD40 Signaling and Promotes V γ 9V δ 2 T cell-Mediated Antitumor Responses in Human
208 B-cell Malignancies. *Cancer Immunol Res.* 2021;9(1):50-61. doi:10.1158/2326-6066.CIR-
209 20-0138
- 210 37. Ganesan R, Chennupati V, Ramachandran B, Hansen MR, Singh S, Grewal IS. Selective
211 recruitment of $\gamma\delta$ T cells by a bispecific antibody for the treatment of acute myeloid
212 leukemia. *Leukemia.* 2021;35(8):2274-2284. doi:10.1038/s41375-021-01122-7
- 213 38. Weerdt I de, Lameris R, Ruben JM, et al. A Bispecific Single-Domain Antibody Boosts
214 Autologous V γ 9V δ 2-T Cell Responses Toward CD1d in Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia.
215 *Clin Cancer Res.* 2021;27(6):1744-1755. doi:10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-20-4576
- 216 39. van Diest E, Hernández López P, Meringa AD, et al. Gamma delta TCR anti-CD3
217 bispecific molecules (GABs) as novel immunotherapeutic compounds. *J Immunother*
218 *Cancer.* 2021;9(11). doi:10.1136/jitc-2021-003850
- 219 40. Lai AY, Patel A, Brewer F, et al. Cutting Edge: Bispecific $\gamma\delta$ T Cell Engager Containing
220 Heterodimeric BTN2A1 and BTN3A1 Promotes Targeted Activation of V γ 9V δ 2+ T Cells
221 in the Presence of Costimulation by CD28 or NKG2D. *J Immunol.* 2022;209(8):1475-1480.
222 doi:10.4049/jimmunol.2200185
- 223 41. Lameris R, Ruben JM, Iglesias-Guimaraes V, et al. A bispecific T cell engager recruits both
224 type 1 NKT and V γ 9V δ 2-T cells for the treatment of CD1d-expressing hematological
225 malignancies. *Cell Rep Med.* 2023;4(3):100961. doi:10.1016/j.xcrm.2023.100961
- 226 42. van Diest E, Nicolassen MJT, Kramer L, et al. The making of multivalent gamma delta TCR
227 anti-CD3 bispecific T cell engagers. *Front Immunol.* 2022;13:1052090.
228 doi:10.3389/fimmu.2022.1052090
- 229 43. Lamb LS, Bowersock J, Dasgupta A, et al. Engineered drug resistant $\gamma\delta$ T cells kill
230 glioblastoma cell lines during a chemotherapy challenge: a strategy for combining
231 chemo- and immunotherapy. *PLoS One.* 2013;8(1):e51805.
232 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0051805
- 233 44. Lamb LS, Pereboeva L, Youngblood S, et al. A combined treatment regimen of MGMT-
234 modified $\gamma\delta$ T cells and temozolomide chemotherapy is effective against primary high
235 grade gliomas. *Sci Rep.* 2021;11(1):21133. doi:10.1038/s41598-021-00536-8
- 236 45. Wang Y, Han J, Wang D, et al. Anti-PD-1 antibody armored $\gamma\delta$ T cells enhance anti-
237 tumor efficacy in ovarian cancer. *Signal Transduct Target Ther.* 2023;8(1):399.
238 doi:10.1038/s41392-023-01646-7
- 239 46. Li L, Lu S, Liang X, et al. $\gamma\delta$ TDEs: An Efficient Delivery System for miR-138 with Anti-
240 tumoral and Immunostimulatory Roles on Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma. *Mol Ther*
241 *Nucleic Acids.* 2019;14:101-113. doi:10.1016/j.omtn.2018.11.009

- 242 47. Wang Y, Zhu J, Yu W, et al. Allogenic $\gamma\delta$ T cell and tumor cell fused vaccine for
 243 enhanced immunotherapeutic efficacy of osteosarcoma. *J Bone Oncol.* 2020;21:100214.
 244 doi:10.1016/j.jbo.2018.100214
- 245 48. Li H-K, Wu T-S, Kuo Y-C, et al. A Novel Allogeneic Rituximab-Conjugated Gamma Delta
 246 T Cell Therapy for the Treatment of Relapsed/Refractory B-Cell Lymphoma. *Cancers*
 247 (*Basel*). 2023;15(19). doi:10.3390/cancers15194844
- 248 49. Straetemans T, Kierkels GJJ, Doorn R, et al. GMP-Grade Manufacturing of T Cells
 249 Engineered to Express a Defined $\gamma\delta$ TCR. *Front Immunol.* 2018;9:1062.
 250 doi:10.3389/fimmu.2018.01062
- 251 50. Johanna I, Straetemans T, Heijhuurs S, et al. Evaluating in vivo efficacy - toxicity profile
 252 of TEG001 in humanized mice xenografts against primary human AML disease and
 253 healthy hematopoietic cells. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2019;7(1):69. doi:10.1186/s40425-
 254 019-0558-4
- 255 51. Kierkels GJJ, Scheper W, Meringa AD, et al. Identification of a tumor-specific allo-HLA-
 256 restricted $\gamma\delta$ TCR. *Blood Adv.* 2019;3(19):2870-2882.
 257 doi:10.1182/bloodadvances.2019032409
- 258 52. Johanna I, Hernández-López P, Heijhuurs S, et al. TEG011 persistence averts
 259 extramedullary tumor growth without exerting off-target toxicity against healthy tissues
 260 in a humanized HLA-A*24:02 transgenic mice. *J Leukoc Biol.* 2020;107(6):1069-1079.
 261 doi:10.1002/JLB.5MA0120-228R
- 262 53. Strijker JGM, Pscheid R, Drent E, et al. $\alpha\beta$ -T Cells Engineered to Express $\gamma\delta$ -T Cell
 263 Receptors Can Kill Neuroblastoma Organoids Independent of MHC-I Expression. *J Pers*
 264 *Med.* 2021;11(9). doi:10.3390/jpm11090923
- 265 54. Nishimoto KP, Barca T, Azameera A, et al. Allogeneic CD20-targeted $\gamma\delta$ T cells exhibit
 266 innate and adaptive antitumor activities in preclinical B-cell lymphoma models. *Clin*
 267 *Transl Immunology.* 2022;11(2):e1373. doi:10.1002/cti2.1373
- 268 55. Gentles AJ, Newman AM, Liu CL, et al. The prognostic landscape of genes and
 269 infiltrating immune cells across human cancers. *Nat Med.* 2015;21(8):938-945.
 270 doi:10.1038/nm.3909
- 271 56. Nicolas L, Monneret G, Debard AL, et al. Human gammadelta T cells express a higher
 272 TCR/CD3 complex density than alphabeta T cells. *Clin Immunol.* 2001;98(3):358-363.
 273 doi:10.1006/clim.2000.4978
- 274 57. Mensurado S, Blanco-Domínguez R, Silva-Santos B. The emerging roles of $\gamma\delta$ T cells in
 275 cancer immunotherapy. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol.* 2023;20(3):178-191. doi:10.1038/s41571-
 276 022-00722-1
- 277 58. Dong R, Zhang Y, Xiao H, Zeng X. Engineering $\gamma\delta$ T Cells: Recognizing and Activating on
 278 Their Own Way. *Front Immunol.* 2022;13:889051. doi:10.3389/fimmu.2022.889051
- 279 59. Aparicio C, Acebal C, González-Vallinas M. Current approaches to develop "off-the-
 280 shelf" chimeric antigen receptor (CAR)-T cells for cancer treatment: a systematic review.
 281 *Exp Hematol Oncol.* 2023;12(1):73. doi:10.1186/s40164-023-00435-w
- 282 60. Page MJ, Moher D, Bossuyt PM, et al. PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration:
 283 updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ.* 2021;372:n160.
 284 doi:10.1136/bmj.n160
- 285 61. Murai N, Koyanagi-Aoi M, Terashi H, Aoi T. Re-generation of cytotoxic $\gamma\delta$ T cells with
 286 distinctive signatures from human $\gamma\delta$ T-derived iPSCs. *Stem Cell Reports.*
 287 2023;18(4):853-868. doi:10.1016/j.stemcr.2023.02.010
- 288 62. Zeng J, Tang SY, Wang S. Derivation of mimetic $\gamma\delta$ T cells endowed with cancer
 289 recognition receptors from reprogrammed $\gamma\delta$ T cell. *PLoS One.* 2019;14(5):e0216815.

- 290 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0216815
- 291 63. Zhang X, Ng YY, Du Z, et al. V γ 9V δ 2 T cells expressing a BCMA-Specific chimeric
292 antigen receptor inhibit multiple myeloma xenograft growth. *PLoS One*.
293 2022;17(6):e0267475. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0267475
- 294 64. Frieling JS, Tordesillas L, Bustos XE, et al. $\gamma\delta$ -Enriched CAR-T cell therapy for bone
295 metastatic castrate-resistant prostate cancer. *Sci Adv*. 2023;9(18):eadf0108. Published
296 May 3, 2023.
- 297 65. Wang Y, Ji N, Zhang Y, et al. B7H3-targeting chimeric antigen receptor modification
298 enhances antitumor effect of V γ 9V δ 2 T cells in glioblastoma. *J Transl Med*.
299 2023;21(1):672. doi:10.1186/s12967-023-04514-8
- 300 66. Harrer DC, Simon B, Fujii S-I, et al. RNA-transfection of $\gamma\delta$ T cells with a chimeric
301 antigen receptor or an $\alpha\beta$ T-cell receptor: a safer alternative to genetically engineered
302 $\alpha\beta$ T cells for the immunotherapy of melanoma. *BMC Cancer*. 2017;17(1):551.
303 doi:10.1186/s12885-017-3539-3
- 304 67. van der Veken LT, Hagedoorn RS, van Loenen MM, Willemze R, Falkenburg JHF,
305 Heemskerk MHM. Alphabeta T-cell receptor engineered gammadelta T cells mediate
306 effective antileukemic reactivity. *Cancer Res*. 2006;66(6):3331-3337. doi:10.1158/0008-
307 5472.CAN-05-4190
- 308 68. Hiasa A, Nishikawa H, Hirayama M, et al. Rapid alphabeta TCR-mediated responses in
309 gammadelta T cells transduced with cancer-specific TCR genes. *Gene Ther*.
310 2009;16(5):620-628. doi:10.1038/gt.2009.6
- 311 69. Marcu-Malina V, Heijhuurs S, van Buuren M, et al. Redirecting $\alpha\beta$ T cells against cancer
312 cells by transfer of a broadly tumor-reactive $\gamma\delta$ T-cell receptor. *Blood*. 2011;118(1):50-59.
313 doi:10.1182/blood-2010-12-325993
- 314 70. Gründer C, van Dorp S, Hol S, et al. γ 9 and δ 2CDR3 domains regulate functional avidity
315 of T cells harboring $\gamma\delta$ 2TCRs. *Blood*. 2012;120(26):5153-5162. doi:10.1182/blood-
316 2012-05-432427
- 317 71. Shimizu K, Shinga J, Yamasaki S, et al. Transfer of mRNA Encoding Invariant NKT Cell
318 Receptors Imparts Glycolipid Specific Responses to T Cells and $\gamma\delta$ T Cells. *PLoS One*.
319 2015;10(6):e0131477. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0131477
- 320 72. Straetemans T, Gründer C, Heijhuurs S, et al. Untouched GMP-Ready Purified
321 Engineered Immune Cells to Treat Cancer. *Clin Cancer Res*. 2015;21(17):3957-3968.
322 doi:10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-14-2860
- 323 73. Rischer M, Pscherer S, Duwe S, Vormoor J, Jürgens H, Rossig C. Human gammadelta T
324 cells as mediators of chimaeric-receptor redirected anti-tumour immunity. *Br J*
325 *Haematol*. 2004;126(4):583-592. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2141.2004.05077.x
- 326 74. He K, You H, Li Y, Cui L, Zhang J, He W. TCR γ 4 δ 1-engineered $\alpha\beta$ T cells exhibit effective
327 antitumor activity. *Mol Med*. 2016;22:519-529. doi:10.2119/molmed.2016.00023
- 328 75. Deniger DC, Switzer K, Mi T, et al. Bispecific T-cells expressing polyclonal repertoire of
329 endogenous $\gamma\delta$ T-cell receptors and introduced CD19-specific chimeric antigen
330 receptor. *Mol Ther*. 2013;21(3):638-647. doi:10.1038/mt.2012.267
- 331 76. Du S-H, Li Z, Chen C, et al. Co-Expansion of Cytokine-Induced Killer Cells and V γ 9V δ 2 T
332 Cells for CAR T-Cell Therapy. *PLoS One*. 2016;11(9):e0161820.
333 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0161820
- 334 77. Fisher J, Abramowski P, Wisidagamage Don ND, et al. Avoidance of On-Target Off-
335 Tumor Activation Using a Co-stimulation-Only Chimeric Antigen Receptor. *Mol Ther*.
336 2017;25(5):1234-1247. doi:10.1016/j.ymthe.2017.03.002
- 337 78. Benveniste PM, Roy S, Nakatsugawa M, et al. Generation and molecular recognition of

338 melanoma-associated antigen-specific human $\gamma\delta$ T cells. *Sci Immunol*. 2018;3(30).
339 doi:10.1126/sciimmunol.aav4036

340 79. Capsomidis A, Benthall G, van Acker HH, et al. Chimeric Antigen Receptor-Engineered
341 Human Gamma Delta T Cells: Enhanced Cytotoxicity with Retention of Cross
342 Presentation. *Mol Ther*. 2018;26(2):354-365. doi:10.1016/j.ymthe.2017.12.001

343 80. Xiao L, Chen C, Li Z, et al. Large-scale expansion of $V\gamma 9V\delta 2$ T cells with engineered
344 K562 feeder cells in G-Rex vessels and their use as chimeric antigen receptor-modified
345 effector cells. *Cytotherapy*. 2018;20(3):420-435. doi:10.1016/j.jcyt.2017.12.014

346 81. Polito VA, Cristantielli R, Weber G, et al. Universal Ready-to-Use Immunotherapeutic
347 Approach for the Treatment of Cancer: Expanded and Activated Polyclonal $\gamma\delta$ Memory
348 T Cells. *Front Immunol*. 2019;10:2717. doi:10.3389/fimmu.2019.02717

349 82. Fisher J, Sharma R, Don DW, et al. Engineering $\gamma\delta$ T cells limits tonic signaling associated
350 with chimeric antigen receptors. *Sci Signal*. 2019;12(598). doi:10.1126/scisignal.aax1872

351 83. Janssen A, Villacorta Hidalgo J, Beringer DX, et al. $\gamma\delta$ T-cell Receptors Derived from
352 Breast Cancer-Infiltrating T Lymphocytes Mediate Antitumor Reactivity. *Cancer Immunol*
353 *Res*. 2020;8(4):530-543. doi:10.1158/2326-6066.CIR-19-0513

354 84. Rozenbaum M, Meir A, Aharony Y, et al. Gamma-Delta CAR-T Cells Show CAR-Directed
355 and Independent Activity Against Leukemia. *Front Immunol*. 2020;11:1347.
356 doi:10.3389/fimmu.2020.01347

357 85. Fleischer LC, Becker SA, Ryan RE, Fedanov A, Doering CB, Spencer HT. Non-signaling
358 Chimeric Antigen Receptors Enhance Antigen-Directed Killing by $\gamma\delta$ T Cells in Contrast
359 to $\alpha\beta$ T Cells. *Mol Ther Oncolytics*. 2020;18:149-160. doi:10.1016/j.omto.2020.06.003

360 86. Ang WX, Ng YY, Xiao L, et al. Electroporation of NKG2D RNA CAR Improves $V\gamma 9V\delta 2$ T
361 Cell Responses against Human Solid Tumor Xenografts. *Mol Ther Oncolytics*.
362 2020;17:421-430. doi:10.1016/j.omto.2020.04.013

363 87. Ichiki Y, Shigematsu Y, Baba T, et al. Development of adoptive immunotherapy with KK-
364 LC-1-specific TCR-transduced $\gamma\delta$ T cells against lung cancer cells. *Cancer Sci*.
365 2020;111(11):4021-4030. doi:10.1111/cas.14612

366 88. Zhai X, You F, Xiang S, et al. MUC1-Tn-targeting chimeric antigen receptor-modified
367 $V\gamma 9V\delta 2$ T cells with enhanced antigen-specific anti-tumor activity. *Am J Cancer Res*.
368 2021;11(1):79-91. Published January 1, 2021.

369 89. Johanna I, Hernández-López P, Heijhuurs S, et al. Adding Help to an HLA-A*24:02
370 Tumor-Reactive $\gamma\delta$ TCR Increases Tumor Control. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12:752699.
371 doi:10.3389/fimmu.2021.752699

372 90. Ferry GM, Agbuduwe C, Forrester M, et al. A Simple and Robust Single-Step Method for
373 CAR-V $\delta 1$ $\gamma\delta$ T Cell Expansion and Transduction for Cancer Immunotherapy. *Front*
374 *Immunol*. 2022;13:863155. doi:10.3389/fimmu.2022.863155

375 91. Sánchez Martínez D, Tirado N, Mensurado S, et al. Generation and proof-of-concept for
376 allogeneic CD123 CAR-Delta One T (DOT) cells in acute myeloid leukemia. *J*
377 *Immunother Cancer*. 2022;10(9). doi:10.1136/jitc-2022-005400

378